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Postulating grounds for school Social Work in India : A Review

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Abstract

With the increase in the range, frequency and nature of school problems that are reported in India, a suitable and promising social work practice is required to address them. School social work practice which stands on empirical evidence and informed framework has been a specialized practice in schools especially in the European nations to address at risk students concerns. This practice has thus caught on from the western countries to many Asian countries. But in India, the practice has not matured owing to absence of advocacy and requisite research. This paper is an endeavor to underline the scope of such a practice in the Indian context. It also attempts to make us understand the concept of school social work, essentialities of its services and magnificence of the professionals associated with such practice in dealing with many problems and issues which arise in school as a whole.

Keywords: School social work, School social workers, School mental health.

Introduction

A child's most formative period is spent in school, where tales of nostalgic experiences are ever cherished throughout the life. According to Freudian theory of personality, early childhood experiences shape our personality based on how consciously and unconsciously these experiences are processed within the developmental stages of a human being. The psychological and social transition from being a child to becoming an adult is also full of events with concrete thinking, lack of abstract reasoning capabilities and problem solving skills to becoming emotionally independent by overcoming challenges to behavioral change and expanding problem solving skills. Both these periods are spent in school; hence the root manifestation as human beings takes place in our school journey. Those who could respond or conform to the school environment are winners and those who could not do it effectively drop out. In contemporary society, there are many hardships which makes it difficult to cherish those nostalgic moments of school life. To preserve the significant congruity of early as well as later childhood experiences, school social workers are always at the

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forefront. But the problem is the undermined identity of school social worker in India. School social work as a profession suffers from stunted growth in India. In our country, counseling and guidance services are emphasized through trained teachers and school social work has not reached anywhere significant in its practice form unlike that found in its genesis in America or even the other western nations.

School Social Work Practice and the School Social Worker

School social work practice encompasses services for school children and youths which identify and improve the dysfunctional transactions that seriously interfere in the constructive use of school experiences by building on their individual strengths and coping capacities; and improve overall school conditions for all students. School social work is a complex and specialized field of social work which focuses on coordinating the efforts of schools, families and communities for helping students improve their academic achievement and thus enhance their social, emotional and behavioral competence by using its unique ecological perspective of viewing the person in environment (Costin, 1981, Essex et al.,

2016). It is thus a spectrum of tasks which serve the school children, youths, their families, teachers, administrators of school and the community through direct and indirect services. According to School Social Work Association of America (SSWAA), the direct services are the interventions for at risk students to help them with school related concerns which range from stress, bullying, truancy, dropout, harassment, sexuality issues, psychiatric issues, medical issues, family issues, economic issues, and rehabilitative services for disadvantaged children as well. Among the indirect services are multidisciplinary team collaboration, community outreach, assistance to families and teachers, school improvement planning, rehabilitative services planning, etc. Presented briefly below is the history of school social work and its genesis in the United States of America (SSWAA, n.d.).

School social work set its roots during the year 1906–1907 at the same time in New York, Boston, Hartford, and Chicago. They were called “visiting teachers”. The foundation of the essence of school social work was laid in 1931 when these visiting teachers were appointed by a school system in Rochester to enhance the cooperation between the home and school so that forces outside the school system shouldn’t hinder the endeavor to provide education to the children. The scope for school social work expanded with the widening scope of the compulsory attendance laws. Casework was practiced as a changing vehicle for maladjusted children (Constable, 2009). School social work as a

specialty has also been established by the NASW by-laws in 1955. In the U.S Office of Education, school social work became a specialist position in 1959 (Dupper, 2003). The period of 1975 to 1997 marked the crucial years for school social work because on the one hand school social work was gaining its importance through legislations and on the other hand it was developing more into a specialized service. For the first time, the importance of school social work was recognized and codified in The Education for All Handicapped Children Act in 1975 (Dupper, 2003; Kelly, Raines, Stone, Frey, 2010). The 1980s and 1990s marked the inclusion of the school social worker in more legislations.

School social workers were included as qualified personnel in Part H of the Education of the Handicapped Act Amendments of 1986, the Early Intervention for Handicapped Infants and Toddlers, and the Elementary and Secondary School Improvement Amendments of 1988. The American Education Act of 1994, regarded as the major piece of legislation, also included school social worker to achieve eight national goals laid in the Act, of which the major objectives were research promotion, consensus building, and systemic change, to ensure equality of educational opportunities for all students. Furthermore, two pieces of legislation – The Individuals with Disabilities Education Amendment Act of 1997 (formerly known as The Education for All Handicapped Children Act) and No Child Left Behind Act Amendment of 2006 have influenced the job and role of school social worker (Allen-Meares, 2013).

The present school social work as a profession has strong base from these legislations and reforms which brought additional changes to its overall practice. The Individuals with Disabilities Education Amendment Act of 1997 introduced Individualized Education Program (IEP) as a major tool to understand a student's involvement and progress and emphasized Positive Behavioral Support (PBS) interventions to address classroom management, school climate, social skills and violence prevention (Dupper, 2003). In

1971, the Washington State Board of Education adopted guidelines in a system model for competency- based certification of the school social worker and the goal was to ascertain that the candidate has achieved the competence equivalent to the BSW level of training (Ellis and Bryant, 1976). In 1992, NASW developed the school social work credentialing exam which is 'The Educational Testing Service' and for the first time Allen- Meares was administered. Also in 1992 NASW Education Commission Task Force revised the standards for school social workers. Many state associations have come up in the US that have set standards for highly qualified school social worker and introduced post-masters mentorships to provide permanent certification to the school professionals who are highly qualified (Constable, 2009). In 2012, NASW has again revised the guidelines for school social worker. More recently, in 2015, the Congress replaced the most controversial 'No Child Left Behind Act' with 'The Every Student Succeeds Act' and this new Act has molded new roles for

school social worker and other specialized instructional support personnel in identifying low scores of school students and minority students, improving school literacy, ensuring school safety, supporting mental and behavioral health of students among other roles (Strobach, 2015).

Multifaceted Functions of School Social Worker

School social workers are the professionals available to students, their families and communities to initially identify and provide interventions. According to Openshaw (2007), school social workers are the generalist practitioners who must have the requisite skills for working with individuals, groups, and communities. SSWAA have defined school social worker on their official portal as those who “are trained mental health professionals with a degree in social work, who provide services related to a person’s social, emotional and life adjustment to school and/ or society. School social workers are thus the link between the home, school and community in providing direct as well as indirect services to students, families and school personnel to promote and support student’s academic and social success” (SSWAA, n.d.).

It is essential that school social workers are trained in cultural diversity, systems theory, social justice, advocacy, child rights, risk assessment & intervention, consultation & collaboration, and clinical intervention strategies to address the mental health needs of students. They work to remove barriers to learning which result due to inequality, poverty, inadequate health care, and violence. They work with teachers, administrators, parents, and other educators to provide coordinated interventions and consultation which are designed from evidence-based framework of practice to retain students in school and help families access the support needed to promote students’ success. They often focus on providing support to the vulnerable populations of students who are at a high risk of dropping out of school and truancy, the students who are homeless, foster, and migrant children, students transitioning between school and treatment programs or the juvenile justice system for rehabilitative services, or students who experience domestic violence and sexual abuse. School social workers must coordinate with the interdisciplinary teams with information from collateral sources and complete assessment of students at risk. They have a crucial role in crisis intervention when there are problems of suicide threats, deaths of students, any family members or teachers, and any other school crisis situations (Costin, 1973; Open shaw, 2007; Kelly et al., 2010). To design and implement school-based programs to promote a positive school climate among all students is another specialty about school social work (Costin, 1978).

School social worker works with the entire student body to identify students in need of more intensive interventions and connect these students to additional services in the community where needed. They serve as a resource

person to the Principal and other educators, providing consultation and training on identifying students with mental health problems and extend to provide referral services when they are sought. Working more closely with individual students and their families, school social workers also create a bridge between the school and the community with the other members of interdisciplinary team of mental health professionals. This coordination is very important in a successful school and community partnership to maximize limited resources, facilitate better service delivery, and maintain communication between partners. School social worker uses the helping measures which are based on and grow out of values and knowledge of social work profession and they have an advantage of implementing the ecological perspective of practice.

Alarming Statistics

The first incidence study done in India examined the incidence of childhood psychiatric disorders in the community setting. It was six years follow up study which reports that the incidence of child psychiatric disorders to be 18/1000 per year among the 10-17 years old adolescents and the rate could be said to range between 18-37/1000/year. According to the study, the pattern of psychiatric disorders fell into the category of neurotic, stress related and affective disorders; personality and behavior disorders. They conclude that these conditions are basically adult disorders which had their onset during childhood. It has been reported that the peak hazard rate for major depression, mania, OCD, phobias and drug and alcohol disorders was in childhood or adolescence (Malhotra, Kohli, Kapur and Pradhan, 2009).

In a study to ascertain the prevalence of depressive disorders among school going adolescents (13-18 years) in Chandigarh in north India, it showed that a significant proportion of them suffered from depression which is around 40%. The study also reports that the associated factors of depression are modifiable and suggests that the modification is required in schools as well as in home environment (Singh, Gupta and Grover, 2017). Another study explored the factors associated with depression. According to the study, the factors associated with the development of depression in children and adolescents have been clinic-based or school-based. Researchers evaluated life events, demographic factors, or clinical factors associated with the development of depression. These factors can be categorized as those related to studies or education, relationship issues in the familial context, familial issues, economic difficulties, and other factors (Grover, Raju, Sharma and Shah, 2019).

In India, the young people in the age group of 10-24 years are precious resources but at the same time they are vulnerable to many factors which threats or affect their well-being. It is estimated that India's population has more than 30 % of young people of age 10-24 years, which means that every third person belongs to this age-group (Singh and Gopalkrishna, 2014). In studying the

health and behavior problems among young people, Singh and Gopalkrishna (2014) found nutritional disorders (both malnutrition and over-nutrition), tobacco use, harmful alcohol use, other substance use, high risk sexual behaviors, stress, common mental disorders, injuries such as road traffic injuries, suicides, violence, behavioral problems, poor health, mental and neurological disorders affect this population.

Bhatia, Vij and Madhura (2013) in their study of stress level among adolescents in Government and Public schools of Delhi found that stress as a cause of anxiety within them affects their academic performances. Stress in examinations, leisure time-activities, home and school environment, sleep pattern and also consumption of junk food before and during the examinations are the reasons for increasing stress and anxiety among the adolescents. The study also informs that mental health of adolescents going to private schools are found significantly better than those who attend government schools.

In a study based in Kolkata city of India in order to understand anxiety among adolescents, it is found that anxiety prevails more in boys than girls. Also medium of instruction flares a role and it was found that students of Bengali medium are more anxious than those of English medium. Adolescents of working mother of middle class are more anxious and a substantial proportion of them perceived that they did not receive quality time from fathers and mothers. A majority of them added that they did not feel comfortable to share their personal issues with parents (Deb and Walsh, 2010).

An exploratory study on the experience of bullying in India reports that males have higher incidence of bullying. Their psychosocial functioning assessment had shown depression and antisocial personality problems at a higher rate. The study finds that people with bullying experiences tend to have more psychological problems compared to those who had not faced bullying. It is suggested in the study that bullying experiences lead to long-term consequences for the victims which are needed to be identified at school level and plan interventions for them (Bhuyan and Manjula, 2019).

These studies are not the definite list of alarming statistics of the health, behavioral and psychiatric problems of children and adolescents in India, but they are exemplary. It is evident from these that the incidence of children requiring mental health services are quite high. If these are addressed in schools, efficacy of preventive interventions as well as treatment interventions gets finer (Openshaw, 2009).

Fissures, lacunae and argument

School social work practice appeared in India during the late nineteen fifties but unfortunately has almost died. The practice came to light through the placement of student social workers in schools for fieldwork placements and through some bold attempts by the associations of trained social workers in New

Delhi, Parent Teachers Associations, and the Municipal Corporations of New Delhi and Mumbai. This field has not attained the stability ability and the level it deserves mainly because of a sheer lack of scientific studies conducted in this field (Gandhi, 1990). However, it gradually gave away as no research was being done on it to either prove or disprove its essence. Therefore, the importance of this practice could not be put forth before the policy makers. Literature review also reveals that in India, there is very less work done as a part of research practice to promote school social work. India realized the potentialities and need for a school social worker during the 1970s but these services almost don't exist now (Allen-Meares et al., 2013). It appears to lack a strong identity in our country and there is very less awareness of the need for these services or even its scope in the Indian schools. However, guidance and counseling services in some form, quite distant from what a trained social worker would follow; is provided by some of the educational boards in the country. National Council for Educational Research and Training (NCERT) emphasized teachers as facilitators and introduced diploma courses for teacher training as counselors in schools. After the training the teachers become Education and Vocational Guidance Counselors (EVGC) (NCERT, 2015). In India, teacher training programs are more popular and hence such a practice is adopted.

There are more than 1.6 million schools under the 54 different educational boards in the country, including the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE), Council for the Indian School Certificate Examinations (CISCE) which is the umbrella for ICSE and ISC and the various State Educational Boards. A relatively smaller number of schools in the country are affiliated to various other boards like the Madrasa boards of various states, the Central Tibetan School Administration, International Baccalaureate (IB) and Autonomous School. In Council for the Indian School Certificate Examinations (CISCE) rules for affiliation, there is a guideline for appointing Counselor and Special Educator among the personnel (CISCE, 2013). Even in a Circular by CBSE, the board has directed to all its affiliated schools to appoint a full-time counselor for regular and periodic psychological counseling sessions for every student in the school (CBSE,

2012). But so far there is no explicit mention of school social work services which is more extensive including counseling. CBSE is the first board of education in the country which has provisions for psychological counseling services to the stakeholders since 1998. Its counseling programs runs in two phases: Phase-I- Counseling services are provided through multiple modes which includes telephonic counseling, support materials and tutorials on CBSE website and newspaper at the time of preparations and during examinations, and Phase-II at the time of declaration of results. After Life Skill Education (LSE) got recognition in the National Policy of India, CBSE is the first board to adopt and incorporate LSE in curriculum as Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) for the IX and X standards with

the grading system. CBSE laid guidelines for the teachers and conducts training of teachers on LSE. Inadequate teaching- learning resources, lack of training of teachers on LSE, time- constraints, inadequate evaluative measures of qualitative skills are some of the issues related to LSE in the case of CBSE (Behrani, 2016). Thus there is an entanglement in perception as well as implementation of social work services with those of counselors thus perplexing the practitioners as well as policy makers.

Presently, there is no study which tells us how school social work that arose has diminished and why. Seth (2001) says social workers in schools are found preferred for counseling and home-visits initially, but gradually they are preferred for community services for which they are mostly engaged in Socially Useful Productive Work (SUPW) and in community work which is a part of it. School counselors are preferred for counseling as the Principal reported the inadequacies on the part of social worker and thus the role of school social worker has emerged as community service teacher. A study by Julia Punnackapadavil and K. Hemalatha (2016) shows that many school counselors are professional social workers who have a high awareness of the skills required by professional counselors attached to schools in Kerala. Counseling which is one of the services of school social work gained attention but the holistic practice of school social work remained undiffused. Thus, school social work services and school social workers' contributions are almost unidentified by the school education system in India. However a few of the schools social work services are being provided such as counseling and career guidance, but the other prominent components of such services remain unidentified. There is a problem of too many professionals, paraprofessionals, self-proclaimed counselors and psychotherapists purporting to offer services that eclipses the role of a social worker. Many non-professional social workers are providing parts of the school social work services because there are overlapping roles. On the other hand, trained social workers have been appointed to provide limited school social work services but have been referred to by different nomenclatures such as counselor. It creates a dilemma when a school social worker is labeled as counselor and such labeling also delimits the other important functions of school social work apart from counseling (Leung, 2013). Thus, there is no role definition which differentiates between social workers and non-professional social workers in the eyes of the school system in India. There is no awareness among the policy makers, educational boards, community and various other stakeholders in the Indian education system about the differences among these various disciplines and that, professionals under these disciplines provide unique roles independently.

Laying Grounds for the School Social Worker

School social work services are broader peripherals for better schooling in India, if we see the extent of mental health and at-risk students' concerns and

the suggestions by various authors. It is observed that very few schools in India appoint professional social worker who can reduce the level of stress activating the environment (Rebellow and Asir, 2017). Recently in the draft National Education Policy 2019, emphasis on provision for social workers in schools has been made in the context of reducing school drop outs (MHRD, 2019). But the social workers in school can practice more extensive functions of meeting mental, physical, social and economic needs which are identified in the literature.

A study of guidance and counseling, as emphasized in various policies/curriculum frameworks, indicates that concern for providing guidance and counseling services in schools for school students has continued throughout the years after independence. The provision of guidance services by trained personnel or counselors, or teachers and training of teachers for the purpose has also been emphasized. A number of Education Commissions and Curriculum Frameworks have laid special emphasis on guidance and counseling in school education. Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) of Education, the first Education Commission in independent India also known as Mudaliar Commission, recognized the importance of proper guidance for students as part of education (Mudaliar Commission Report, 1952). Guidance was viewed as both adjective and developmental; therefore it was regarded as an integral part of education and not a special psychological or social service peripheral to educational purpose. Guidance, therefore, was then seen as a continuous process aimed at assisting the individual to make decisions and adjustments from time to time.

CBSE has also laid down in its Circular No. 8 of March 08, 2008 the provisions for full time Counselor at the Secondary and Senior Secondary level (CBSE, 2012). Later, in 2012, another circular was issued which informed the affiliated schools about the amendments in the affiliation bye-laws. It was then changed from “Counselor” to “Health Wellness Teacher” to make it more students/parents friendly. Along with that there has been another addition to the bye-laws, appointment of Health wellness teacher for full time; and part time for school of 300 strengths in Class XI-XII (CBSE, 2012). In rule 53.5 of affiliation bye-laws of Circular no. 20/2014 dated 6th February, 2014 it is mentioned that the qualification of “ health wellness teacher” should be Graduate/ Post Graduate in psychology or Post Graduate in Child Development or Graduate / Post Graduate with Diploma in Career Guidance and Counseling. But a candidate with BSW/MSW can also do equal justice to the position of ‘Health wellness teacher’. In fact the expectancies from a ‘health wellness teacher’ can be performed more justifiably by a trained social worker. This is the care argument of this paper.

NCERT and RMSA Project Cell presented Guidelines for Guidance and Counseling to support States/UTs for planning interventions related to guidance and counseling at the secondary stage under RMSA (NCERT, 2015). Even in the guidelines, inefficiency to identify the appropriate measures is

observed because simply guidance and counseling are not enough to deal with the present issues and challenges of school children. More specialized services are needed to cater to their needs and concern. Only guidance and counseling cannot serve the mental health issues. Students with untreated mental health issues may develop more significant problems which can greatly impact their educational experience and result in poor educational outcomes and possibly dropping out of school. The plan proposes full time counselors at district level committee to help the trained teachers as counselors. It speaks of candidates from the liberal arts or with a post graduate degree in education favorably but completely undermines the prospects of school social worker or professional social workers who are experts in evidence-based practice.

Sahu (2014) in his book has analyzed the extent of mental health problems among school children in India and suggested that the whole gamut of childhood and adolescent psychiatric problems 'can be cited, observed, elicited and dealt well in school settings'. The author further suggested that it is better that we must gear school mental health program from non- clinical perspective and that the time has come to make the educational bodies more responsive to the contributions of other professionals like school social worker. He also highlighted schools of social work across the country offer traditional and popular specialization, but not school social work in India.

It has been explained that without any assured job market for the young trainees in social work and psychology, the professional opportunities of working in child mental health gets depleted. The author analyzed that the number of psychiatric social workers, with advanced pre-doctoral level training in psychiatric social work from mental health or medical institutions, available in the country will not be adequate to handle school mental health programs in the entire country. So social workers at Master level and having any specialization can be encouraged to work and contribute. Sahu (2014) has also stated that we need one school social worker for every 1,000 students, but it may not be achievable in the short term. So the realistic approach can be worked out by planning along with the educational boards and the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD). He suggested that the existing mental health policy makers need to form a separate task force for school mental health and thus promote school mental health programs. The author has laid more meaningful suggestions that there is an urgent need for social work institutions to start a specialization of school social work and popularize it as a career for post graduate students in social work and the state ought to have a clear policy on mental health in schools and link it with the National Mental Health Policy and the MHRD (Sahu, 2014).

Afterthoughts

It can be finally concluded that a breakthrough is required in terms of school social work in India. It requires popularization among the different types and levels of institutions; both as a career option and as a necessary profession. This can have the cumulative effect of promoting healthy transactions within and outside the school environment that can have long lasting impressions upon the child. Looking at the problems that are being faced by the school going children in India, school social work can bring qualitative changes in their lives. Over a period of hundred years it has earned the fame of becoming a specialized practice owing to research on it and the accountability of the school social worker practicing worldwide. In India the relevance of school social worker lies in the light of its knowledge of practice and arising situations demanding such professional to meet the needs of school children.

References :

- Allen-Meares P., Montgomery, K. L., & Kim, J. S. (2013). School-based social work interventions: A cross- national systematic review. *Social work*, 58(3), 253-262.
- Behrani, P. (2016). Implementation aspects of life skills education program in central board of secondary education schools. *International Education and Research Journal*. 2(3). Pp. 68–71
- Bhatia, R., Vij, S., & Madhura, D. (2013). A Study of Stress Level among Adolescents in Government and Public Schools of Delhi. *Journal of Indian Education*. 39(3), 90-108.
- Bhuyan K., & Manjula M. (2017). Experiences of Bullying in Relation to Psychological Functioning of Young Adults: An Exploratory Study. *Indian Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 33, 240-249.
- Central Board of Secondary Education, Delhi (2012). CBSE update (from 8.3.2005 to 31.12.2011), Compendium of CBSE Circulars, Vol.1 Retrieved from [http://cbseacademic.nic.in/web_material/CBSE-UpdatesCompendium_of_CBSE%20Circulars\)Vol- I.pdf](http://cbseacademic.nic.in/web_material/CBSE-UpdatesCompendium_of_CBSE%20Circulars)Vol- I.pdf).
- Central Board of Secondary Education, Delhi (2013). Circular No.:07/2013, Amendment /Addition in the Affiliation Bay-Laws of the Board-reg. February 18, 2013. Retrieved from http://cbseaff.nic.in/cbse_aff/Circular.htm
- Constable, R., Massat, CR., McDonald, S., & Flynn, JP. (2009). *School Social Work Practice, Policy and Research*, Sixth Edition. Lyceum Books, INC.Social Work, 39(5), 560–565.
- Costin, L.B. (1981). School social work as specialized practice. *Social Work*, 22(1), 36-43.
- Costin, L.B. (1978). Social work services in schools: Historical perspectives and current directions. Continuing education series #8, 1–34. Washington, DC: NASW.

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Deb, S. & Walsh, K. (2010). Anxiety among High School Students in India: Comparisons across Gender, School Type, Social Strata and Perceptions of Quality Time with Parents. *Australian Journal of Educational & Developmental Psychology*, 10, 18- 31.

Department of Educational Psychology & Foundations of Education & RMSA Project Cell, National Council of Educational Research and Training. *Guidance and Counseling: Guidelines for States (Draft)*. January 2015. Retrieved from www.ncert.nic.in/Guidelines_for_Guidance_and_Counseling.pdf.

Dupper, D. (2003). *School social work: Skills and Interventions for Effective Practice*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.

Ellis, J., & Bryant, V. (1976). Competency-based certification for school social workers. *Social Work*, 21(5), 381-385.

Essex, EL., Yamano, N., & Massat, CR. (2016). Making School social work visible, viable and valued. In Carol Rippey Massat, Michael S. Kelly & Robert Constable (Eds) *School Social Work: Practice, Policy, and Research* (8th ed.) pp. 419– 436. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

Gandhi, A. (2003). *Social Work in Educational Settings. Social Work Intervention with Individuals and Groups*. IGNOU Publications. New Delhi.

Grover, S., Raju, V. V., Sharma, A., & Shah, R. (2019). Depression in Children and Adolescents: A Review of Indian studies. *Indian journal of psychological medicine*, 41(3), 216–227. doi:10.4103/IJPSYM.IJPSYM_5_19

Hossain MM., & Purohit N. (2019). Improving Child and Adolescent Mental Health In India: Status, Services, Policies, and Way Forward. *Indian J Psychiatry*, 61, 415-419.

Kelly, M. S., Berzin, S. C., Frey, A., Alvarez, M., Shaffer, G., & O'Brien, K. (2010a). The state of school social work: Findings from the National School Social Work Survey. *School Mental Health*, 2, 132-141. doi: 10.1007/s12310-010-903.4-5

Kelly, M. S., Raines, J.C., Stone, S., & Frey, A. (2010b). *School social work: An evidence- informed framework for practice*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

Kelly, M. S., Raines, J. C., Stone, S., & Frey, A. (2010c). *The State of School social work: Findings from the National School social work Survey*. *School Mental Health*. Springer.

Kelly, M. S., Raines, J. C., Stone, S., & Frey, A. (2010d). *School social work: An evidence-informed framework for practice*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Kumar, D., Bharath, S., Hirisave, U. Agarwal, S., & Shah, H. (2015). *School mental health programs in India*.

In S Kutcher, Y.Weii, & M. Weist (Eds.), *School Mental Health: Global Challenges and Opportunities* (pp. 95-104). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Leung, CT. (2013). The time before dawn –the discursive nature of school social work development in china. In Wing Hong Chui (Ed.) *School social work: current practice and research*. pp. 1–22. New York, NY: Nova Science Publishers, Inc.

Malhotra, S., Kohli, A., Kapoor, M., & Pradhan, B. (2009). Incidence of Childhood Psychiatric Disorders in India. *Indian journal of psychiatry*, 51(2), 101–107.

Ministry of Education, Government of India. Report of the Secondary Education Commission, Mudaliar Commission Report. June 1953. Retrieved from [www.teindia.nic.in/.../Reports/ Secondary Education_ Commission Report.htm](http://www.teindia.nic.in/.../Reports/Secondary_Education_Commission_Report.htm)

Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (2014). National Mental Health Policy.

Retrieved from [http://www.mohfw.nic.in/index1.php? lang=1&level=2 & sublinkid=4723 & lid=2964](http://www.mohfw.nic.in/index1.php?lang=1&level=2&sublinkid=4723&lid=2964)

Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India. (2019). Draft National Education

Policy of 2019 (Revised). Retrieved from <https://mhrd.gov.in> › draft-national-education-policy-2019-revised

Openshaw, L. (2007). *Social work in schools: Principles and practice*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press

Punnackapadavil, J., & K, Hemlatha. (2016). Awareness of Professional Skill Requirement among school counselors. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 5 (13), 153-155.

Rebellow, M. M. R., & Asir, SDA RM. (2017). Stress among School Going Adolescents. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 77-79

Sahu, K.K. (2014). *Mental Health and Social Work Practice in India: A Historical Perspective*. In Francis, A.P. (Ed.), *Social Work in Mental Health: Areas of Practice, Challenges and Way Forward* (pp. 62-85). New Delhi: Sage.

School social work Association of America. School social workers' Role (n.d). Retrieved from <https://www.sswaa.org/school-social-work?page=721>

School social work Association of America. School social workers' Role in Addressing Students' Mental Health Needs and Increasing Academic Achievement. (n.d). Retrieved From <https://nyssswa.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/Role-of-SSWs-in-Addressing-Mental-Health-Needs-Increasing-Academic-Achievement.pdf>.

Seth, N. (2001). *A study of social workers and counselors in schools of Delhi*. Ph.D Thesis. Department of Social Work, Jamia Milia Islamia, New Delhi.

Sharma, E., & Kommu, JV. (2019). Mental Healthcare Act 2017, India: Child and adolescent perspectives. *Indian J Psychiatry*, 61, 756-762.

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Singh, M., Gupta, M. & Grover, S. (2017). Prevalence & factors associated with depression among school going adolescents in Chandigarh, north India.

Singh, S., & Gopalkrishna, G. (2014). Health Behaviors & Problems among Young People in India: Cause for concern & call for action. *Indian J Med Res*, 140, 185-208.

Strobach, KV. (2015, December 17) The Every Student Succeeds Act and School Psychologists. [Web log post] Retrieved from <https://www.nasponline.org/research-and-policy/policy-matters/the-every-student-succeeds-act-and-school-psychologists>